

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD) Assay Kit Instruction

(Product Code: A001-1 T-SOD)

1. Brief Introduction

This assay kit is designed to measure the activity of superoxide dismutase based on the xanthine oxidase method and is suitable for the samples like serum/plasma, cerebrospinal fluid, pleural effusion, peritoneal fluid, renal dialysis fluid, urine, red blood cells, white blood cells, platelets, cultured myocardium cells, cultured neoplasm, and other cells or subcellular components (mitochondria or microsome etc.). Also, researchers can use this kit for the measurement of samples such as micro-organisms, drugs, food, beverages and cosmetics.

2. Significance of Measurement

Superoxide dismutase plays an important role in the balance of oxidation and anti-oxidation in vivo and can eliminate the superoxide anions in vivo to avoid cell damage by the superoxide anions.

3. Principle of Measurement

Super oxide anions generated as the byproduct of Xanthine Oxidase catalyzed Xanthine oxidation and the anion can oxidize hydroxylamine to nitrite which appears to be amaranth purple in the presence of chromogenic agent and thus the absorbance at certain wavelength can be detected by spectrophotometer. The presence of SOD in the system specifically inhibits the oxidization caused by super oxide anions and because of it, fewer nitrite anions are generated. This would lower the absorbance of the sample tube compared to the reference tube without SOD and the SOD activity can be calculated with the formula given. There are two types of SODs in higher animal cells: CuZn-SOD and Mn-SOD with total SOD activity equals to the sum of the activities of both type. Pretreatment

should be done to remove the activity of Mn-SOD in sample while retain its original CuZn-SOD activity.

4. Apparatus and Reagents Required

1. Spectrophotometer to measure the absorbance at 550 nm
2. Thermostatted water bath or gas bath (at 37°C)
3. Tabletop centrifuge
4. Air displacement pipettes
5. Double distilled water (DDW)
6. Acetic acid (analytic grade, ≥99.5%)

5. Reagent Composition and Preparation

I. 100T/48 Samples

Reagent	Type	Format	Preservation Environment
I	Stock Buffer	1 Bottle×10ml	4°C for 1 year
		(The solute may be crystallized at low temperature and under such circumstance, the precipitant should be warmed to dissolve before use)	
	Buffer Preparation: Dilute the stock buffer with double distilled water (DDW) to the final volume of 100ml and this buffer solution can be preserved at 4°C for 1 year.		
II	Substrate Solution	1 Bottle×10ml	4°C for 1 year
III	Stroma Solution	1 Bottle×10ml	4°C for 1 year
IV	Stock Enzyme Solution	2 Vials×350μl	4°C (cannot be frozen)
	Diluent	1 Bottle×10ml	4°C for 6 months
	Enzyme Solution Preparation: Dilute the stock enzyme solution using diluent with the ratio 1:14 and it is recommended to prepare the exact amount needed. The excess can be preserved at 4°C but cannot be frozen.		
V	1 Vial of Powder		4°C for 1 year
	Reagent V Solution Preparation: Dilute with 70-80°C DDW to a final volume of 75ml, the solution can be preserved at 4°C for 1 year without light struck.		
VI	1 Vial of Powder		4°C for 1 year
	Reagent VI Solution Preparation: Dilute with DDW to a final volume of 75ml, the solution		

	can be preserved at 4°C for half a year without light struck.
Chromogenic Agent	Preparation of Chromogenic Agent: Blend the reagent V, reagent VI solution and acetic acid with the ratio 3:3:2 and the chromogenic agent can be preserved at 4°C for 3 months. Note: Acetic acid used is analytical reagent with purity≥99.5%

II. 50T/ 24 Samples

Reagent	Type	Format	Preservation Environment
I	Stock Buffer	1 Bottle×5ml	4°C for 1 year
		(The solute may be crystallized at low temperature and under such circumstance, the precipitant should be warmed to dissolve before use)	
	Buffer Preparation: Dilute the stock buffer with double distilled water (DDW) to the final volume of 50ml and this buffer solution can be preserved at 4°C for 1 year.		
II	Substrate Solution	1 Bottle×5ml	4°C for 1 year
III	Matrix	1 Bottle×5ml	4°C for 1 year
IV	Stock Enzyme Solution	1 Vial×350μl	4°C (cannot be frozen)
	Diluent	1 Bottle×5ml	4°C for 6 months
	Enzyme Solution Preparation: Dilute the stock enzyme solution using diluent with the ratio 1:14 and it is recommended to prepare the exact amount needed. The excess can be preserved at 4°C but cannot be frozen.		
V	1 Bottle of Powder		4°C for 1 year
	Reagent V Solution Preparation: Dilute with 70-80°C DDW to a final volume of 37.5ml, the solution can be preserved at 4°C for 1 year without light struck.		
VI	1 Bottle of Powder		4°C for 1 year
	Reagent VI Solution Preparation: Dilute with DDW to a final volume of 37.5ml. The solution can be preserved at 4°C for half a year without light struck.		
Chromogenic Agent	Preparation of Chromogenic Agent: Mix the reagent V, reagent VI solution and acetic acid with the ratio 3:3:2 and the chromogenic agent can be preserved at 4°C for 3 months. Note: Acetic acid used is analytical reagent with purity≥99.5%		

Note: All ratios are expressed as volume ratios

6. Procedure of Measurement

I. Total-SOD Pre-measurement for Optimum Quantity of Sample Used

Extract 10µl, 30µl and 50µl sample fluid respectively and measure the absorbance with the components and procedures listed below. Calculate the inhibition rate of each sample quantity with one single reference.

$$\text{Inhibition rate} = (A_{\text{Reference}} - A_{\text{Sample}}) / A_{\text{Reference}}$$

The sample quantity with the inhibition rate within 45%-50% should be used for the rest of the measurement.

Note: Were the results too high, the samples can be diluted for another pre-measurement.

II. Measurement

Reagent (ml)	Total SOD Reference (A)	Total-SOD (B)
Buffer Solution	1.0	1.0
DDW	a	
Sample		a
Reagent II	0.1	0.1
Reagent III	0.1	0.1
Enzyme Solution	0.1	0.1
Vortex till Fully Mixed and Warm at 37°C for 40 min		
Chromogenic Agent	2	2

Mix thoroughly, and set aside the mixture at room temperature for 10 min. After that, zero the spectrophotometer with DDW and measure the absorbance at 550nm with 1cm light path.

Note: a is an arbitrary number and represents the optimum volume determined at the previous step.

Note: The procedures should be strictly followed and different types of reagents cannot be mixed before the measurement.

7. SOD Activity Calculation for Fluids

I. Definition

One SOD activity unit is defined as 1ml fluid among which the inhibition rate of SOD is 50%.

II. Calculation Formula

Total – SOD Activity
(U/ml)

$$= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \times CoD$$

Note: CoD represents the coefficient of dilution before the measurement.

III. **Example**

30µl untreated plasma was measured and the absorbance values of the reference and sample tube are 0.476 and 0.281 respectively.

Total – SOD Activity
(U/ml)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \times CoD \\ &= \left(\frac{0.476 - 0.281}{0.476} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{3.33ml}{0.03ml} \times 1 \\ &= 90.95U/ml \end{aligned}$$

Culture medium 100µL was measured and the absorbance values of the reference and sample tube are 0.473 and 0.312 respectively.

Total – SOD Activity
(U/ml)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \times CoD \\ &= \left(\frac{0.473 - 0.312}{0.312} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{3.40ml}{0.10ml} \times 1 \\ &= 23.15U/ml \end{aligned}$$

8. SOD Activity Calculation for Tissue homogenate

I. Definition

One SOD activity unit is defined as 1mg tissue protein among which the inhibition rate of SOD is 50%.

II. Calculation Formula

Total – SOD Activity
(U/mg)

$$= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \div \frac{C_{protein}}{mg/ml}$$

III. Example

- 1% mouse hepatic tissue homogenate was prepared and measured and the absorbance values were 0.510 and 0.242 respectively. Also, the protein concentration of the homogenate was 1.075 mg/ml.

Total – SOD Activity
(U/mg)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \div \frac{C_{protein}}{mg/ml} \\ &= \left(\frac{0.510 - 0.242}{0.510} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{3.33ml}{0.03ml} \div 1.075mg/ml \\ &= 323.6U/mg \end{aligned}$$

Note: For plant tissues, the definition of the SOD activity unit can be re-defined as 1 g tissue among which the inhibition rate of SOD is 50%.

And for this definition, calculation formula is shown below:

Total – SOD Activity
(U/g)

$$= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \div \frac{W_{tissue/g}}{V_{homogenate/ml}}$$

Example:

50µL 10% Arabidopsis leaf homogenate was measured and the absorbance values were 0.540 and 0.272 respectively.

Total – SOD Activity
(U/g)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \div \frac{W_{tissue/g}}{V_{homogenate/ml}} \\ &= \left(\frac{0.540 - 0.272}{0.540} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{3.35ml}{0.05ml} \div \frac{0.1g}{0.9ml} = 594.1U/g \end{aligned}$$

9. SOD Activity Calculation for Red Blood Cells

I. Pretreatment

The pretreatment of red blood cells include a 50µL whole blood being

separated by centrifugation at 500-1000rpm for 10 min, and the pellets being hemolyzed by distilled water and hemoglobin being extracted by 0.2mL distilled water, 0.1mL 95% ethanol and 0.1mL chloroform.

II. Definition

One SOD activity unit is defined as 1g hemoglobin in 1 ml solution among which the inhibition rate of SOD is 50%.

III. Calculation Formula

Total – SOD Activity
(U/gHb)

$$= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times V_{Reaction\ Total} \times \frac{0.3mL}{V_{Sample}} \div V_{Blood} \div \frac{C_{Hemoglobin}}{mg/ml}$$

IV. Example

10μL hemoglobin extracted by the method mentioned below was measured and the absorbance values were 0.465 and 0.293 respectively. And the hemoglobin concentration in whole blood is 105g/L (0.105g/L).

Total – SOD Activity
(U/gHb)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_A - OD_B}{OD_A} \right) \div 50\% \times V_{Reaction\ Total} \times \frac{0.3mL}{V_{Sample}} \\ &\div V_{Blood} \div \frac{C_{Hemoglobin}}{mg/ml} \\ &= \left(\frac{0.465 - 0.293}{0.465} \right) \div 50\% \times 3.31 \times \frac{0.3mL}{0.01} \div 0.05 \\ &\div 0.105 = 1.399 \times 10^5 U/gHb \end{aligned}$$

10.SOD Activity Calculation for Serum from Hyperlipemia Patients

I. Pretreatment

Serum from mild hypercholesterolemia patients: Serum can be diluted with the same amount of saline before the measurement.

Serum from moderate hypercholesterolemia patients: Serum should be diluted with the same amount of saline and half amount of 95% ethanol

before the measurement.

Serum from severe hypercholesterolemia patients: Take 50µL serum and blended with 200µL saline and 150µL ethanol. Then add 150µL chloroform and centrifuge at 3500 rpm for 10 min. Extract the supernatant for measurement.

II. Procedures

Reagent (ml)	Total-SOD (A)	Reference (B)
Buffer Solution	1.0	1.0
DDW		
Sample	a	
Reagent II	0.1	0.1
Reagent III	0.1	0.1
Enzyme Solution	0.1	0.1
Vortex till Fully Mixed and Warm at 37°C for 40 min		
Chromogenic Agent	2	2
Sample		a

Mix thoroughly, and set aside the mixture at room temperature for 10 min. After that, zero the spectrophotometer with DDW and measure the absorbance at 550nm with 1cm light path.

III. Definition

One SOD activity unit is defined as 1ml fluid among which the inhibition rate of SOD is 50%.

IV. Calculation Formula

Total – SOD Activity
(U/ml)

$$= \left(\frac{OD_B - OD_A}{OD_B} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \times CoD$$

V. Example

Rabbit serum was pretreated and 150 µ L supernatant was measured with the absorbance values were 0.262 and 0.434 respectively.

Total – SOD Activity
(U/ml)

$$\begin{aligned} &= \left(\frac{OD_B - OD_A}{OD_B} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{V_{Reaction\ Total}}{V_{Sample\ Fluid}} \times CoD \\ &= \left(\frac{0.434 - 0.262}{0.434} \right) \div 50\% \times \frac{0.345}{0.15} \times 8 \\ &= 145.8U/ml \end{aligned}$$

11. Notes

1. All reagents should be prepared one day before the assay to ensure the complete dissolution of the reagents. Prepared reagents can be preserved at 4° C for 3 months (except the reagent IV) and should be placed at RT for 30 min before usage.
2. The incubation period is 40 min and can be prolonged to 45 min were the ambient temperature below 20°C.
3. Two blank tubes are required for the assay and the mean value should be used for the following calculation.
4. EDTA cannot be the anti-coagulant as it can react with metal ions in SOD to decrease the activity.

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